

MANAGEMENT OF A TRAUMATIZED OPEN APEX TOOTH WITH MINERAL TRIOXIDE AGGREGATE APEXIFICATION

AUTHOR NAMES

1.Dr Apurva Jamodkar

Post Graduate Student , Department Of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics ,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur

2.Dr Ambar Raut

Professor And Head Of Department , Department Of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics ,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur

3.Dr Himanshi Solanki

Reader, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur

4.Dr Sanchi Kadbe

Senior Lecturer, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur

5.Dr Shweta Tugnayat

Post Graduate Student , Department Of Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics ,
Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur

ABSTRACT- Trauma to the dentition during the period of root formation results in incomplete development of root resulting in open apex. Henceforth it becomes necessary to induce or create an apical barrier against, which the obturating material can be condensed. Traditionally, calcium hydroxide is considered as the gold standard to induce apexification. Due to certain drawbacks such as very long treatment period, possibility of tooth fracture, and incomplete apical barrier formation, it is being replaced by materials, which have a more predictable outcome like mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA).

Mineral trioxide aggregate appears to be a promising alternative to calcium hydroxide apexification because of its high biocompatibility, superior sealing ability and reduced treatment time. Here, we report a case of 18-year-old boy who came with a chief complaint of pain in upper front teeth. Apical stop was created with mineral trioxide aggregate by apexification and the root canal was obturated with thermoplasticized guttapercha.

INTRODUCTION To stop re-infection, the main goal of endodontic therapy is to completely occlude the root canal space. Without the natural constriction at the end of the root canal, teeth with incomplete root development from trauma, caries, and other pulpal pathosis are more difficult to control when it comes to filling materials. Apexification, also known as root end closure, has been recommended as an alternative to traditional root canal therapy due to the absence of an apical constriction.^{1,2}

The term apexification refers to the process of creating a calcific barrier in a root that has an open apex or the ongoing apical growth of teeth that have necrotic pulp and incomplete roots.³ The original material of choice for apexification has been calcium hydroxide, which has undergone several modifications over a period of five to twenty months in order to promote the establishment of a calcific barrier.^{4,5} Numerous writers have proven its effectiveness even when an apical lesion is present.^{6,7}

This treatment modality's unexpected and frequently protracted duration poses a number of difficulties, such as the temporary coronal restoration's susceptibility to re-infection, and has a number of drawbacks, including its variable treatment duration (average 12.9 months) the inability of the patient to recall treatment, treatment delays, and an elevated risk of tooth breakage following prolonged application of calcium hydroxide dressings.⁸⁻¹⁰

Because of its favorable sealing ability, bacteriostatic activity, biocompatibility, and ability to fill root ends, mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) has been suggested as a material appropriate for one visit apexification. MTA provides the barrier that allows warm gutta-percha to condense vertically in the remaining portion of the root canal, particularly in teeth with necrotic pulps and open apices.^{11,12} In order to provide an apical stop that would aid in obturation, MTA was utilized in this case study to apexify open apex instances.

CASE REPORT- A 18 year old male patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental college and Hospital with a chief complaint of pain anterior tooth with a history of trauma 10 years ago. Clinical examination showed a Ellis Class IV fracture with remaining coronal tooth structure around 50%, with 21 compromising esthetics as well as function. Radiographic examination demonstrated the presence of open apex (Fig.1). The tooth did not respond to the pulp vitality tests. The available treatment options were discussed with the patient and root canal therapy using MTA as an apical barrier was selected. Patient was informed with the treatment plan and a consent form was obtained. In the first session, coronal access was prepared with a round bur under rubber-dam isolation. The WL was estimated by periapical radiography using a #90 K-file. (Fig.2). Then canal was gently debrided with large H-files (Mani, Prime Dental, Mumbai) and copious amounts of 5% sodium hypochlorite. Calcium hydroxide intra canal medicament was placed for one week to disinfect the root canal. At the second appointment, calcium hydroxide was flushed with 5% sodium hypochlorite and rinsed with saline. Final irrigation was done with 2% chlorhexidine and the canal was dried with paper points. MTA (Dentsply, Tulsa Dental, Johnson City, USA) was mixed according to the manufacturer's instructions and carried to the canal with an amalgam carrier. Apical plug of 4mm of MTA was placed and confirmed radiographically (Fig. 3). A sterile cotton pellet moistened with sterile water was placed over the canal orifice and the access cavity was sealed with Cavit (3M ESPE, Seefeld, Germany). After 72 hours, the hard set of MTA was confirmed and the remainder of the root canal was obturated with thermoplasticized guttapercha (Obtura II, Obtura Spartan, Fenton, Missouri, USA) and AH-Plus sealer (Dentsply, DeTrey, Konstanz, Germany). At the same visit, the access cavity was restored with composite (Ceram-x Duo, Dentsply, De-Trey, Konstanz, Germany) (Fig. 4).

Fig.1. Pre- operative Radiograph

Fig.2. Working length Radiograph

Fig.3. MTA Apical Plug Radiograph

Fig.4. Post Obturation Radiograph

DISCUSSION: A permanent incisor tooth that can be characterized as immature is one whose tip is open. For these teeth to undergo root canal therapy, a root end closure procedure is needed to create a complete calcific barrier at the tooth's apex against which a guttapercha filling can be compressed. This prevents sealant or guttapercha from passing past the apex and into the periapical tissues. The goal of the

root canal procedure is to get rid of the infection's microbiological source. Thus, calcium hydroxide intracanal medication and the antibacterial irrigants sodium hypochlorite and chlorhexidine were utilized for a week.

When used for this duration, the latter has demonstrated the ability to eradicate bacteria from the root canal. Because the goal is to remove debris from the root canal walls rather than "shape" the canal—the canals of young, non-vital teeth are wide and have weak dentinal walls, H files were utilized. MTA was created in 1990 at Loma Linda University by Torabinejad and associates. It comes in grey and white MTA. Composition includes Tricalcium silicate, tricalcium aluminate, tetracalcium aluminoferrite, calcium sulfate dihydrate, and silicate oxide. It is radioopaque due to the presence of bismuth oxide. The material's pH is 12.5 after three hours. Comparable to IRM and Super EBA in terms of compressive strength, MTA reaches its maximum compressive in 72 hours. Because MTA reaches its peak strength during this time, obturation was performed after 72 hours. Divergent open apices complicate MTA adaption in teeth with necrotic pulps. In their 2003 evaluation of MTA implantation, Aminoshariae et al. used both hand and ultrasonic condensation; they found that hand condensation produced less voids and greater adaptability than ultrasonic condensation. Therefore, in these instances, MTA was compacted at the apex by hand condensation. Because thermoplasticized guttapercha does not result in excessive compaction stresses on the thin dentinal walls of an immature tooth, it was used for obturation in the apexification protocol with MTA.

CONCLUSION: In endodontic therapy, MTA has a wide spectrum of uses, from pulpotomy to apexification. Reduced appointment frequency, appropriate apical seal formation, and superior biocompatibility are the main benefits of this material as an apical barrier. One of MTA's apexification material indicators was illustrated in this article. While more investigation is required to identify potential applications for MTA, its application in endodontics seems to be advantageous and very promising.

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